

THE IMPORTANCE OF USING INTERNET RESOURCES IN THE PROCESS OF TEACHING ENGLISH LANGUAGE IN SCHOOL

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Annotation: At present, priority importance is given to the issues of communication, interactivity, authenticity of communication, language learning in cultural settings, autonomy of education and humanism. These principles make it possible for culture to develop competence as a component of communicative competence. The ultimate goal of teaching foreign languages is to teach a free orientation in a foreign language environment and the ability to respond adequately in different situations. In this article, opinions and suggestions are made about the importance of internet resources in teaching English language in school.

Keywords: English, school, students, Internet resources, electron resources, quality of education, techniques.

Today, with the use of Internet resources, new methods are opposed to the teaching of traditional foreign languages. In order to teach communication in a foreign language, you need to create real, real-life situations that stimulate the study of material and develop adequate behavior (that is, the authenticity of communication is called principal). New technologies, in particular the Internet, are trying to correct this error. A communicative approach is a strategy that simulates communication, aimed at consciously understanding the material and ways of working with it, creating a psychological and linguistic preparation for communication.

It is not particularly difficult for students to implement a communicative approach on the Internet. The communicative task should invite students to discuss a problem or question, the students not only share information, but also evaluate them. The main criterion that allows this approach to be distinguished from other types of educational activities is that students independently choose linguistic units

for the formation of their own thoughts. In the communicative approach, the use of the Internet is very well encouraged: its purpose is to interest the students in learning a foreign language by accumulating and expanding their knowledge and experience.

One of the main requirements for teaching foreign languages with the use of Internet resources is the creation of interaction in this lesson, which is usually called interactivity in the methodology. Interactivity is "the combination, coordination and filling of communicative purpose and result efforts with the help of speech tools." Through authentic language teaching, the Internet helps to formulate speech skills and skills, and also provides a sincere interest in teaching vocabulary and grammar and therefore efficiency. Interactivity not only creates real situations from life, but also forces students to respond adequately to them in a foreign language.

One of the technologies that provide student-oriented education is the project method as a way of developing creativity, cognitive activity and independence. The typology of the projects is diverse. Projects can be divided into mono projects, collective, spoken, concrete, written and Internet projects. In real practice, it is often necessary to deal with mixed projects in which there are research projects, creative, practice-oriented and informative characters. The project work language is a multifaceted approach in learning and covers reading, listening, speaking and grammar. The project method helps students actively develop independent thinking and direct them to joint research work.

In my opinion, project-based teaching teaches children to collaborate, while learning to collaborate educates moral values such as mutual assistance and the ability to empathize, shape creativity and students. In general, in the process of teaching the project, there is no separation of teaching and learning.

The project method involves the development of students' communication skills, culture of treatment, the ability to formulate ideas concisely and easily, the ability to tolerate the opinions of communication partners, the ability to obtain information from a variety of sources, process using modern computer technologies, create a language environment that contributes to the emergence of a natural need.

Grammatical is taught in greater depth in the middle stage than in the first, and pupils are given activities and assessments based on grammar concepts. Computer and phone learning applications are also excellent for primary and secondary school education. Talk (English speaking practice), Daily English, Learn English (English master), and how to speak real English are some examples. These applications are built to include all aspects of reading, listening, and testing. Another wonderful approach to concentrate in your leisure time is to record new words on a phone voice record. Showing more English subtitles and cartoons is also an effective technique of teaching the language.

It should be assumed that the game is, first and foremost, a method of teaching. Students are eager to participate in fun lessons, they want to win, and the teacher uses them to educate the students. The student wants to believe he can play, speak, listen, understand, and write in English. We all know that in today's educational system, the student must be a subject. Focusing on more interactive ways will improve educational effectiveness. One of the most crucial needs for English classes is that students learn to think for themselves.

In conclusion, Modern language education aims to develop a more cultured individual with the ability to self-analyze and systematize new knowledge. Innovative approaches are essential to updating the overall system. With this in mind, instructors can become acquainted with the most advanced approaches, which they can then mix and apply in their work to create considerable improvement in the education system. Many businesses are taking things to the next level by utilizing multimedia capabilities to communicate and receive information. The success of the entire educational process is determined by the employment of computers and other gadgets.

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